

PERSUASION STRATEGIES IN LAWYER'S SPEECH: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Khujaniyazova Hilola Turaevna

Senior Teacher, Researcher

Uzbek State University of World Languages

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Abstract. This thesis presents a comparative analysis of persuasive rhetorical strategies employed in lawyer's speech in English and Uzbek languages. Based on Aristotle's concepts of *logos*, *ethos*, and *pathos*, the study investigates the differences and similarities within the juridical discourse of both languages. While English juridical speech prioritizes a formal, logical, and evidence-based approach, Uzbek juridical rhetoric tends to emphasize emotional influence, traditional forms of address, and cultural values. The research provides a practical basis for improving juridical rhetorical competence and enhancing effective cross-linguistic juridical communication.

Keywords: lawyer's speech, persuasive strategy, juridical rhetoric, *logos*, *ethos*, *pathos*, comparative analysis, courtroom discourse, language and culture

ADVOKAT NUTQIDA ISHONTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI: INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA QIYOSIY TAHLIL

Xujaniyazova Hilola Turayevna

Katta o'qituvchi, ilmiy tadqiqotchi

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti

Abstrakt. Ushbu tezisdav advokat nutqining ishontirishga yo'naltirilgan ritorik strategiyalari ingliz va o'zbek tillari misolida qiyosiy tahlil etiladi. Aristotelning *logos*, *ethos*, *pathos* kabi ishontirish vositalari asosida har ikki tildagi huquqiy diskursdagi farqlar va o'xshashliklar ko'rib chiqiladi. Ingliz tilida rasmiy, mantiqiy va dalillarga suyanghan uslub ustuvor bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida hissiy ta'sir, an'anaviy murojaatlar va madaniy xususiyatlar ustun turadi. Tadqiqot huquqiy ritorik mahoratni takomillashtirish, hamda tillararo huquqiy muloqotni samarali tashkil etish uchun amaliy asos yaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: advokat nutqi, ishontirish strategiyasi, huquqiy ritorika, *logos*, *ethos*, *pathos*, qiyosiy tahlil, sud diskursi, til madaniyati

Lawyer's speech, as a vital component of juridical rhetoric, is a powerful instrument that serves to uphold justice in society. This genre demands not only juridical knowledge but also rhetorical skill aimed at convincing the audience—whether a judge or jury. The primary function of a lawyer's speech is to uncover the truth and thereby influence the court's decision in favor of the client. In this process, the effective use of persuasive strategies plays a decisive role. These strategies differ in scope and application across cultures and languages. Particularly, the comparative study of persuasive strategies in English and Uzbek courtroom discourse constitutes a significant area of modern juridical linguistics.

Among the main persuasive strategies are the categories proposed by Aristotle—*logos* (logic), *ethos* (speaker's credibility), and *pathos* (emotional appeal) — which are widely used in juridical speeches (Aristotle, trans. 2007). In English juridical discourse, special emphasis is placed on *logos*. For instance, expressions like "It is evident from the testimony that..." are used to draw logical conclusions based on evidence (Tiersma, 1999). This reflects a mature

juridical style grounded in structured reasoning. Uzbek lawyers also rely on logical reasoning; however, they often incorporate pathos — emotional appeal and humanitarian considerations—into their arguments. For example: “My client is the sole breadwinner of a large family; his punishment would bring hardship to the entire household,” (“Himoyamdagi shaxs katta oilaning boquvchisi, uning jazolanishi butun oilasini qiynalishiga olib keladi.”) which conveys not only a juridical but also an ethical message.

Ethos, the credibility of the speaker, plays a significant role in both languages. English lawyers highlight their professional authority through a formal, balanced tone: “As a representative of the Crown, I must stress the importance of integrity.”

Uzbek lawyers, by contrast, emphasize their standing through traditional honorific expressions: “Honorable members of the court, my life experience and sense of professional responsibility do not allow me to remain indifferent to this matter.” (“Muhtaram sud hay’ati, mening hayot tajribam va kasbiy mas’uliyat hissini bu masalaga befarq bo’lishimga yo’l qo’ymaydi.”).

Moreover, stylistic features of each language play an important role in persuasion. In English, a formal and neutral tone is dominant, often employing passive constructions and conditional structures to influence the audience without direct pressure (Gibbons, 2003). For example: “It could be argued that...” or “There is a reasonable doubt...” allows the speaker to avoid imposing an opinion, instead encouraging the listener to arrive at a conclusion. In Uzbek, more assertive expressions, direct address, emotive vocabulary, comparisons, and proverbs are frequently used to appeal to the audience’s feelings.

Cultural factors are also crucial. In the Anglo-Saxon juridical tradition, values such as juridical precedent, objective evidence, and the presumption of innocence significantly shape the content and expression of juridical speech. In Uzbekistan, juridical rhetoric is influenced by national values, family relationships, and appeals to public opinion (Rakhimov, 2020). These cultural nuances define structural differences in rhetorical construction.

In conclusion, both juridical systems employ persuasion strategies aimed at achieving specific objectives. However, the tools, style, and lexical choices involved vary due to cultural, juridical, and rhetorical differences. English juridical speech is more logic- and evidence-oriented, whereas Uzbek juridical discourse tends to rely on ethical and emotional influence. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of cross-linguistic and cross-cultural features of persuasive rhetoric in juridical contexts and serves as a foundation for enhancing rhetorical competence in juridical practice.

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